

A THEORY OF SPACE AND THE DARK UNIVERSE

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ABSTRACT

Space can be regarded as an entity or viewed as a 3-dimensional framework in which events in nature unfold. The nature of space is largely unknown. We have developed a physical model of space based on a theory that it is a dynamical entity which is quantized in units of λ_s , given by the Planck equation, $E=hc/\lambda$. We call these quanta of space waves "spacinos". From wave-particle duality, they can also be considered as a gas which obey the equation of state, $PV=nRT$. Using a thermodynamic approach, we have constructed a model of the universe in which space participates actively in its evolution. The model differs from that of the Big Bang model and is much simpler. The creation of matter occurs naturally via phase transition of the spacinos. With data on the composition of the universe during cooling, at various cosmic epochs, we have constructed a phase diagram of the model universe which gave an insight on the nature of dark energy and dark matter. Dark Energy is the energy of space. Dark Matter is most likely a plasma state, which was the state of the universe during the photon epoch, before recombination. Both are invisible making them difficult to study; one is transparent to radiation while the other is opaque.

The proposed theory modifies present concepts of vacuum energy and the Cosmological Constant. The acceleration in the expansion of the universe is better attributed to space as a third medium of the universe in place of vacuum. It has an antigravity property, and contributes to the total energy density as a scalar field associated with space quanta.

INTRODUCTION

Space can be looked upon as an entity or part of a conceptual framework in which nature operates. It is widely regarded as the latter. It has been the subject of debate among philosophers, scientists, and mathematicians from Plato to Descartes, Kant, Newton, Leibniz, and others¹. The nature of space is largely unknown. Here we propose a theory of space that considers it as a quantized entity. We apply the theory to develop a simple physical model in which space is an active participant in the evolution of the universe and one of its major components, along with matter and radiation. The model provides an insight on the nature of space and the origin of the dark components of the universe, i.e., dark energy and dark matter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our theory is based on a relationship between energy, E , and space of dimension, λ , as expressed by the Planck quantum energy equation,

$$E=hc/\lambda \quad (1)$$

This is an expression of the equivalence of energy and space which is analogous to that for energy and mass given by the Einstein equation, $E= mc^2$. Thus, energy is inherent in space and space in energy. Space is made up of quantal units, with dimension λ_s , which we shall call "spacinos". They are peculiar to space, distinct from gravitational and electromagnetic waves. The space waves (spacinos) can be viewed as the thread that weaves the fabric of space. From the principle of wave- particle duality, the spacinos can also be thought of as a gas which obeys the equation of state²,

$$PV=nRT. \quad (2)$$

Here P is the pressure of the gas, V the volume, T the temperature, n the number of moles and R the gas constant.

THE EVOLUTION OF THE UNIVERSE

With the above theory we can model the gross features of the evolution of the universe as follows:

The universe started (at time, $t=0$) as a very small volume of compressed gas (the spacinos) at an extremely high pressure and temperature. For example, a mole of gas particles compressed to a volume of $4.2 \times 10^{-33} \text{ m}^3$ (a sphere of 0.1 A^0 radius), at a pressure of $1.95 \times 10^{63} \text{ atm}$ will be at conditions during the Planck epoch with a temperature of 10^{32} K . From this initial state, the gas then expands and cools. As it cools to the appropriate temperature phase transition occurs resulting in the formation of fundamental particles, radiation, nuclei, and atoms. Gravitation causes the formation of galaxies and stars; their clumping results in clusters, local groups and superclusters. Details of the events and transformations involved at the various epochs of the evolution of the universe based on the Big Bang Theory are well documented in books on Cosmology^{4,5,6}. They need not be repeated here. The universe of spacinos continues to expand as we know it.

The model differs somewhat from that of the Big Bang; it is much simpler. It avoids the problem of singularity. The processes of expansion of spacinos and their phase transformation (nucleation and growth) to form matter occur naturally (This is analogous to the formation of snow during a cold winter day); they are orderly and result in a universe which is isotropic and homogeneous. A cosmic inflation stage is not necessary. The process is not as violent as a "big bang"; it is more a "soft swoosh". More importantly, space actively participates in the creation and evolution of the universe, rather than a canvas where nature's landscape and events are portrayed

COMPOSITION OF THE UNIVERSE

Several methods are used to determine the composition of the universe. Results of the WMAP satellite studies³ gave the composition shown in Table I soon after the Big Bang and at present:

Table I-Composition of the Universe

	At the Big Bang	At Present
Dark Matter	63%	25%
Dark Energy	—	71%
Ordinary Matter	12%	4%
Neutrinos	10%	—
Photons	15%	—

The composition during the cosmic evolution is also well documented^{4,5,6}. Table II shows this as a function of pressure (P) and temperature (T) at various times or Cosmic Epoch.

Table II.-Composition of the Universe during its Evolution

<i>Time (after Big Bang)/ (Cosmic Epoch)</i>	<i>Temperature (K)</i>	<i>Pressure (Pa)</i>	<i>Composition</i>
0 to 10 sec/ (Quark,Hadron,Lepton)	$10^{12} - 10^9$	$10^{42} - 10^{27}$	I. Fundamental particles + radiation
10 to 10^3 sec/ (Nucleosynthesis)	$10^{11} - 10^9$	$10^{37} - 10^{27}$	II. Nuclei of H, He,D,Li + radiation
10 sec to 3.8×10^5 yrs/ (Photon to Recombination)	$10^9 - 10^3$	$10^9 - 10^5$	III. Plasma of ionized H, He and e-
3.8×10^5 to 10^9 yrs/ (Dark Ages to Matter dominated)	$3 \times 10^3 - 4$	$10^{-5} - 10^{-20}$	IV. Matter in galaxies,stars space, planets-gases,plasma, solid

10^9 to 13.8×10^9 yrs/
(Dark Energy dominated)

4 - 2.7

10^{-20} - 10^{-21}

V. Dark Energy

At temperatures above 10^{12} K, the universe was a primeval hot gas from which fundamental particles (quarks, leptons, hadrons, protons, neutrons, electrons) and radiation were created. Upon cooling to about 10^{11} K, nucleosynthesis occurred to produce nuclei of H, He Li and D. At about 10^9 K a plasma phase was formed which consisted of electrons and positive ions of H and He. Radiation (photons, neutrinos) was ever present and dominated the early epoch of the universe. Further cooling of the plasma to about 3×10^3 resulted in recombination of electrons with positive ions of H and He, converting the plasma to gases. As the universe (spacinos) continued to expand and cool, matter continued to form which, through the action of gravity, became galaxies, stars, and clusters. The universe cooled to 2.7 K as indicated by the Cosmic Microwave background. The primary constituents of the universe are: gases (H, He), plasma of electrons, protons, and He ions, ordinary matter (gasses, solids, dust, in stars, galaxies, clusters, intergalactic space) and spacinos (gas at all temperatures); radiation is ever present.

Fig. 1- Phase Diagram of Model Universe (Spacinos)

The data shown in Table II give the phases formed during the cooling of the universe. From the data, we have constructed a thermodynamic phase diagram⁷ for our model universe of spacinos. This is shown in Fig.1. (Note that the figure is schematic and the temperature is not drawn to scale in order to highlight the phases formed).

The major phases are: matter (IV, solid, gasses, plasma formed in galaxies, stars, clusters), a plasma phase (III) formed immediately after nucleosynthesis, dark energy (V) and spacinos (gas). Dark matter is not indicated since its nature remains unknown. All phases are in contact with spacinos at all eras of the evolution of the model universe. This is as it should be as space is in contact with all elements of the real universe at all times. At extremely high temperatures and pressures (right end), fundamental particles and radiation are indistinguishable from the hot spacinos; while at low temperature/pressure (left end), dark energy overlaps with the cold spacinos. The phases shown are well supported by experimental data.

DARK ENERGY AND THE EXPANSION OF THE UNIVERSE

Dark energy is an unknown form of energy and is hypothesized to permeate all of space uniformly. It is invisible and difficult to study because it does not interact with radiation, hence cannot be investigated spectroscopically. It only interacts with gravity. Its density is very low, less than ordinary or dark matter, it converts to dark matter, was less in the past than at present, and it functions as anti-gravity. It is believed to be a property of space and causes the accelerated expansion of the universe⁸.

Based on our model, the expansion of the universe could be thought of as the propagation of spacinos driven by the pressure and temperature differential of the hot and cold gas states. This corresponds to a transition of the spacinos from a high energy state, i.e., short λ_s , in eq.1, (small space) to a low energy state, long λ_s , (large space). Space needs to expand! This is a property of space that is anti-gravity, i.e. the pressure of space opposes the force of gravity, hence it is negative.

From Fig.1, one sees that dark energy is a phase that overlaps with a new entity that we have introduced as a component of the universe, i.e., the spacinos; the two phases are indistinguishable. We therefore identify dark energy as the energy of space. The amount of dark energy soon after the Big Bang was relatively small (Table I) because most of the energy of space has been converted to radiation, dark matter and ordinary matter. Its density remains low as the universe expands.

The expansion of our model universe can be treated mathematically in terms of the FLRW (Friedmann-Lemaitre-Robertson-Walker) metric⁴, as had been done with the Big Bang model. The Friedmann equation delineates the contributions of the various components of the universe (matter, radiation, and vacuum) to the total energy density. Based on our model of space, the term "vacuum energy" has lost its meaning; it would be preferable to replace it with the term "energy of space". Thus, the equation expressing the acceleration in the expansion of the universe will then have a contribution from the energy density of space which is now the third substance that constitutes the universe. The equation can be written as,

$$d^2a/dt^2 = -(8/3)\pi G a \{ (1/2) \rho_m + \rho_r + \rho_s \} \quad (3)$$

In the above equation, a is the scale parameter, G the gravitational constant; ρ_m is the mass-energy density of matter, ρ_r that of radiation, and ρ_s that of space. A negative pressure gives rise to a positive term for the contribution of ρ_s , thus causing an acceleration of the expansion. The latter term should now be used in place of the cosmological constant Λ , and the notion of "empty space" can be abandoned. In terms of Field Theory, the space quanta (spacinos) can be thought of as arising from a scalar field⁹, (the space field). They would correspond to the "quintessence" that has been theorized as the substance that comprises dark energy.

An accelerated expansion of the universe cannot be sustained indefinitely in our model since it is a closed system and the expansion is adiabatic. The action of gravity will eventually cause deceleration, reversal, and end in a "big crunch". The only way to sustain an infinite expansion (or a continuously accelerating one) is for the process to be non-adiabatic, i.e., with a continuous leak of energy from an inexhaustible outside source. This means a universe that is open. It is a possibility with our real universe; it is seldom considered and would be difficult to prove; only time will tell.

THE NATURE OF DARK MATTER

Dark matter is said to comprise 83% of the total mass of matter in the universe. At the present time; it is calculated to make up 27% of the total mass-energy of the universe. It remains a mysterious, hypothetical form of matter, whose properties are largely unknown because it neither emits or absorbs electromagnetic radiation. It also moves without friction. It can only be detected through its gravitational effects on the motion of galaxies. It is spread over large areas, like a cloud, around galaxies and clusters; its density decreasing as one moves away from the center⁹. It is also found in filaments between galaxies and clusters¹⁰. It has been observed that ordinary matter traces the path of dark matter; this has been attributed to a strong interaction between ordinary matter and dark matter.

The phase diagram shows that the major phases in the formation of the universe are dark energy, ordinary matter (gasses, solids), and plasma. We have equated dark energy to the energy of space. From the observed properties of dark matter we think it reasonable to make the assignment that dark matter corresponds to the plasma form of matter that existed during the photon epoch, just before recombination. This designation is supported by the WMAP data, mentioned earlier, that dark matter constitutes the major component of the universe soon after the Big Bang. During this time, the universe consisted of a hot plasma of electrons, and ionized H and He. It was opaque and cannot emit or absorb light. This state persisted until about 300,000 years after the Big Bang at which time recombination took place. Furthermore, other characteristics of plasmas match exactly those of dark matter. As a plasma, dark matter hangs around like a cosmic fog around galaxies and clusters, making it invisible and difficult to characterize. That ordinary matter traces the path of dark matter can be explained by the fact that upon recombination of electrons and positive ions in the dark matter plasma, ordinary matter is formed; the plasma evaporates into H and He gasses. Thus ordinary matter follows the trail of dark matter. Filamentation is a characteristic of plasmas; they move without friction,

since the ions do not have strong attractive interaction and move collectively instead¹¹. Moreover, plasma constitutes the major form of matter in the universe, most of it invisible.

NATURE AND PROPERTIES OF SPACE QUANTA

Little is known about the nature and properties of space. The prevailing description is a geometrical one. It is considered as a new coordinate referred to as spacetime; it is distorted by matter and described mathematically in Einstein's General Theory of Relativity. It is rigorous but abstract and does not provide information on the properties of space.

Our theory of space provides a physical picture of this entity. Together with a model universe it has yielded data that match well published, albeit, scanty information on the characteristics of the dark components of the universe. It gives a preliminary glimpse into some of the properties of space quanta, e.g,

- 1). They differ from electromagnetic radiation, hence, cannot be detected by spectroscopic techniques, much like gravitational waves.
- 2). They exert a pressure that counteracts the force of gravity
- 3). They are associated with a scalar field rather than the vector field of electromagnetic waves; in this aspect, it is much like gravity being associated with the gravitational field.
- 4). They are a source of energy in the universe and can transform to radiation and matter; space acts as an energy reservoir in the universe.

CONCLUSION

A quantum theory of space appears to be useful in building a simple physical model that sheds light on our mysterious dark universe. In the model, space is a dynamical entity that actively participates in the creation and evolution of the universe. The components of the universe emanate from the energy of space. A thermodynamic approach, with a phase diagram showing the composition of the model universe, helped elucidate the nature of dark matter and dark energy. The theory modifies present concepts of "empty space", "absolute vacuum" and the Cosmological Constant. It appears appropriate to replace the latter with the energy of space, associated with a scalar field, as the cause of the accelerated expansion of the universe. Dark energy is a plasma form of matter, similar to the state of the universe at the photon epoch, before recombination. Finally, the theory is supported by observation of the Casimir effect¹² which is postulated to originate from "vacuum fluctuations"; it is an inherent property of space in our theory. Further development and refinement of the theory would help better understand the nature of space and its associated space field. It also might be useful in the elucidation of other natural phenomena.

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